

D11.1 WEBPAGE, SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

Acronym:
NEO-CYCLE

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DISCLAIMER

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ABBREVIATIONS

KoM – Kick-off Meeting

LCI – LC Innoconsult

VMU - VYTAUTO DIDZIOJO UNIVERSITETAS

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1. Abstract

LCI collaborates with web developers, graphic designers, videographers, and printing specialists to develop a comprehensive set of communication tools that bolster the visibility and outreach of Project Neo-Cycle. This suite includes branding and communication guidelines, website development, a cohesive visual identity, logo design, presentations, exhibition materials, brochures, flyers, videos, and infographics. Additionally, it incorporates partner-focused dissemination tools such as online logos and a structured clearance procedure for publications.

LCI is also tasked with establishing communication channels tailored to different stakeholder groups. These channels encompass social media platforms (X, LinkedIn, ResearchGate), fostering engagement within the scientific community through publications in esteemed journals, and facilitating participation in project-related events and conferences. With support from partners and content contributions from key participants, LCI will manage and maintain social media channels with weekly updates to ensure consistent outreach and engagement.

VMU (with partners support) will contribute with curriculum and awareness raising tools, also contributing to the preparation of web content, articles, press releases, promotional material, social media messages, dissemination events (conferences, workshops, fairs) and adaption for national level.

2. Logo

A temporary logo was developed for its use in the Kick-off meeting presentation template. LCI collaborated closely with a graphic designer to create multiple logo options that encapsulated the core values of the project, including sustainability, IT waste management, and the upcycling of neodymium magnets.

After thorough internal discussions with the designer, LCI shortlisted the primary logo options. These options were then presented to the Consortium, allowing members to select the most favored design.

The final logo for Project Neo-Cycle was chosen through a voting process conducted during the Kick-off Meeting.

Previous, temporary logo:

The temporary logo consists of the words 'NEO-CYCLE' in a bold, green, sans-serif font. The letters have a slight 3D effect with a darker green shadow underneath.

Options on KoM:

Winner of the voting process:

3. Social media

Social media channels play a crucial role in fostering public engagement and awareness. LinkedIn and X (Twitter) accounts have been created for social communication to different audiences, allowing interactions and discussions with the public. ≥300 followers are

expected in each, following a post publication strategy with key messages, targeting at least 1 post per week as the project advances.

By leveraging these platforms, the project can effectively communicate updates, share research insights, and highlight achievements to a broad audience, including industry stakeholders, policymakers, and the general public. Public communication is vital, because it emphasizes the importance of sustainable practices and the innovative approach to upcycling. Engaging openly on these channels helps building transparency, stimulating collaborations, and inspiring wider adoption of eco-friendly solutions in the technology and waste management sectors.

Image 1. LinkedIn page - <https://www.linkedin.com/company/neo-cycle>

Image 2. X (Twitter) account - https://x.com/neo_cycle

ResearchGate

Each individual researcher can upload their publications to ResearchGate; and LCI will trace and make the list of all the project publications.

4. Webpage

The project website serves as a primary access point for anyone seeking information about Neo-Cycle project. A user-friendly and intuitive interface is essential for guiding users effectively and enhancing their browsing experience. The website will feature various sections that provide an overview of the project, introduce partners, offer resources, and grant access to publicly available results. Additionally, an advanced metrics tool will be integrated to monitor and analyze site traffic, with a target of reaching over 100,000 visitors within three years.

During the development phase, LCI collaborated with a graphic design team to establish the visual direction of the website, ensuring alignment with the project's logo and color scheme. Initial content, including partner introductions, project ambitions, and key milestones, was collected from all consortium partners by LCI and delivered to the design team for integration.

The official website, <https://neo-cycle.eu/>, is currently under construction and undergoing final refinements. The planned launch is set for calendar week 47, with an expected go-live date of November 30, 2024.

ANNEX 1. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION GUIDELINE

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION GUIDELINE

NEO-CYCLE has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement No 101138058.

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1. Summary

The aim of this document is to guide partners in their communication and dissemination activities related to the NEO-CYCLE project.

Communication and Dissemination activities are about informing the European society about the project and its results. The participants of NEO-CYCLE as beneficiaries received money from the EU, more directly from the European Taxpayers, to implement the project detailed in the Grant Agreement. It is expected to communicate how their tax money is being spent. The more these R&D projects and their results are communicated the more trust people have in the system leading to more funding opportunities. Good communication has other benefits too since it can also reach potential buyers and investors, create market demand or reach politicians to modify or create policies to support the development of the market.

It is expected from all beneficiaries of the project to engage in Dissemination and Communication activities to the best of their abilities, this way the project can reach a wide audience. The activities may include but are not limited to: engaging with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based), contributing to inputs on social media, and proactively sharing information about project results. Where possible, partners should

- translate press releases and other communication and dissemination materials into their national languages;
- keep the project partners informed about plans (clearance procedure),
- create lists of local newspapers and journals as well as national media channels that they will try to reach.

2. Communication – informing a broad audience about the project

The aim of communication is to inform and reach out to a broad audience (Citizens, the media and stakeholders) about the progress of the project, highlighting the benefits to society of the research carried out with the public funding of the EU. Communication activities should follow along with the project from the start of the project and should continue even after its termination.

For effective communication, it is needed for the project to differentiate itself from others. It is done by branding. We do this by **using a project acronym and a unique visual identity**.

2.1. Project acronym:

The correct way to mention the project anywhere is by the **project acronym: NEO-CYCLE**. Please use all caps to emphasize the objective of the project.

2.2. Visual Identity:

At the beginning of the project, graphic materials have been created for the project to be differentiated visually. **Partners must use the visual supporting materials (logos, templates and branding) from the start and throughout the lifetime of the project to create a unified and clean look for all communication and dissemination materials.** In case a partner would like to use these materials to help in the visual aspect of their communication they must **contact LCI**, as we can provide templates as well as help in the creation of such materials.

2.2.1. Logo:

2.2.2. Graphic elements:

2.2.3. Colours:

Please note that these colours may not be used in every case. Using them is a guide/suggestion so the materials look standardized.

2.3. Communication channels:

2.3.1. Website:

<https://NEO-CYCLE.eu/>

NEWS

Phasaellus ex justo

Joe Damera | 14-09-2024

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OVERVIEW

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What it is? How does it work?

The website is the number one most important digital information portal of the project. Our website is currently a one-pager that presents the basic information about the project and its objectives. We are constantly updating the website's content to share as much knowledge with the audience as possible. Project partners and their role and achievements in the project will be presented on the site as well as any news relating to the project, its progress or results.

How to use it?

Please share with LCI any information, change, news etc. that you would like to be presented on the site so we can keep the information relevant and up to date. Also, it is generally a good idea to share the link to the website in every communication or dissemination activity so that the public can look more into it.

2.3.2. ResearchGate:

<https://www.researchgate.net>

What it is? How does it work?

ResearchGate is a professional social networking platform tailored for researchers, scientists, and academics, designed to facilitate collaboration, knowledge sharing, and visibility of scientific work. Launched in 2008, it has become a popular space for individuals and institutions in the academic world to share their publications, access others' research, and engage with the global research community. The platform allows users to create profiles showcasing their published work, connect with peers, ask questions, and discuss topics relevant to their field.

How to use it?

Much like Facebook serves as the primary social media hub for personal and business interactions, ResearchGate is a dominant force in academic networking. It helps academics to promote their work, collaborate with peers, and reach new audiences within the scientific community. By making research more accessible, it increases the visibility of ongoing work and facilitates communication across disciplines.

ResearchGate also serves as a dissemination tool for project results, helping to raise awareness, share updates, and drive traffic to institutional pages or publications. Through features like Q&A discussions, profile interactions, and direct messaging, it enables real-time engagement with colleagues worldwide.

In essence, ResearchGate plays a crucial role in scholarly communication, much like Facebook does in the broader social media landscape, enabling quick and efficient interaction, visibility, and engagement with a wide academic audience.

2.3.3. LinkedIn:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/NEO-CYCLE/>

What it is? How does it work?

LinkedIn is an essential social channel for businesses and professionals. Nowadays it is getting popular between EU bodies and funded projects as well. The main focus on LinkedIn is the same as on Facebook, reaching a large general audience, but here the focus is on professional entities. Through the use of LinkedIn, it is possible to gain traction with the help of interacting with fellow researchers.

How to use it?

If you have a LinkedIn account, we would highly advise you to follow the project's account. If you are active on the platform, we would like to you share some thoughts and updates of your own achievements. If you do so, tag the project (**@NEO-CYCLE**) and use the following hashtags: **#NEO-CYCLE #UPCYCLING #HORIZONEUROPE**

2.3.4. X (Twitter):

https://x.com/NEO_CYCLE

What it is? How does it work?

In Europe X is not commonly used, but it is getting more and more popular among the business and scientific community. X is a place where not just celebrities and influencers, but companies and policymakers actively share their thoughts, and updates and follow trends. It is not a place to be extensive with the words as there is a 280-character limit for each tweet.

How to use it?

In case you have an X account we would highly advise you to follow the project's account. In case you would like to share some thoughts on your own please consult with us, tag the project (@NEO-CYCLE) and use the following hashtags: **#NEOCYCLE #UPCYCLING #HORIZONEUROPE**. The main theme we will tweet about are the updates and objectives reached and the milestones of the project. As X is becoming increasingly visual, we suggest posts to include pictures, videos, GIFs or data visualizations to attract attention.

2.4. General Do's and Don'ts:

- ! **Engage!** - Always react to the project's social media activity (Comment, Share, Like)!
- ! **Do not share any sensitive information!** - keep in mind current IPR standards
- ! **Use pictures where it is reasonable!**
- ! **Do not tag the project in personal activity!**
- ! **Do tag the project's social media account or website when posting about the project!**

3. Dissemination - informing stakeholders and the scientific community about the project findings and results

The aim of dissemination is to reach out to stakeholders and relevant audiences (such as scientists, industry and other commercial actors, professional organizations, and policy-makers) to enable a better uptake and use of the project results. All EU-funded projects have an **obligation to disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests**. Implementing strong dissemination activities to increase the visibility of the project, promote the adoption of the catalysts and raise awareness of the importance of magnet recycling/upcycling. Dissemination activities should include publishing achievements such as project milestones, publication of papers, participation on conferences, fairs, workshops, and other related events.

3.1. Obligation of dissemination (GA article 17)

Based on Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in accordance with Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner.

3.2. Open science obligation

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository (e.g. Zenodo) for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

3.3. Policy on publications (CA 8.4)

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 30 calendar days before the publication.

Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

4. Additional tools and rules

4.1. Communication and Dissemination Log

Every partner must enter all communication and dissemination activities into an online document uploaded to the project's Sharepoint platform. The log will serve as the basis for reports which detail the communication and dissemination efforts and will show measurably the impact of the project. It is important to add these activities as soon as they happen and accurately as it is much more difficult to fill it in retrospectively.

4.2. Acknowledgement of EU funding:

The EU emblem should be clearly visible on the website and communication materials (prototypes, leaflets, posters etc.). The emblem should be accompanied by a funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

This is what it should look like:

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How and when to use the disclaimer?

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate): (GA article 17.3)

Disclaimer:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

- 4.3. The European Commission offers various free-of-charge services and tools to support your communication and dissemination activities:

[Research and Innovation success stories:](#)

A collection of the most recent success stories from EU-funded Research & Innovation.

[Horizon Magazine:](#)

The latest news and features about thought-provoking science and innovative research projects funded by the EU.

[Open Research Europe platform:](#)

An open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article revision.

[Horizon Results platform:](#)

A platform for showcasing your research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others.

[Horizon Results Booster:](#)

Free consulting services including a portfolio dissemination and exploitation strategy, business plan development and go-to-market support.

[Innovation radar](#): An initiative that identifies high-potential innovations, based on a data-driven methodology, and assists EU-funded researchers and innovators in reaching the market with their innovation.

If you are interested in using one or more of the above-mentioned tools, please let us know and we can provide further information on how to use them.

4.4.Offline/physical materials:

Ad-hoc/if needed: Flyers, posters,

Besides the ≥ 40 leaflets distributed in each of the physical events, if there is a need for other printed materials such as flyers or posters, LCI can provide help with creating them and their visuals and can send it electronically or can hand it over in printed form at the next occurring project meeting to the partner intending to use them.